

Recruitment text from senior author

Dear [name],

[add personal note]

We are a research team from <Name of the university>. We are studying how Security and Privacy (S&P) researchers consider and discuss the ethical implications of their research. We would like to invite you to a 60 minute interview to share your insights on ethical considerations in your research and within the S&P research community.

The interview will be conducted on zoom. We would like to record the interview and use de-identified transcripts for analysis. Because we are colleagues in the field, the PIs on the project (including myself) will actually only ever read the de-identified transcripts. You can also opt to not be recorded, please let us know in advance if that is the case.

If you're interested in our study, please fill out this survey: <Link for demographics survey and consent form>

Thank you for considering this! We understand that you are very busy, and if you do not wish to participate or do not have time, please simply ignore this email. We might send a follow-up, later, if we haven't heard from you, but the same note applies: we know you are very busy and may not wish to or may not have time to participate, and no reply needed if so.

If you do choose to reply to this email about this project, please Reply-All, just to make sure your response reaches everyone quickly.

[add personal note]

Recruitment text for PhD students

Dear [name],

We are a research team from Paderborn University and the University of Washington. We are studying how Security and Privacy (S&P) researchers consider and discuss the ethical implications of their research. We would like to invite you to a 60 minute interview to share your insights on ethical considerations in your research and within the S&P research community.

The interview will be conducted on zoom. We would like to record the interview and use de-identified transcripts for analysis. You can also opt to not be recorded, please let us know in advance if that is the case.

If you're interested in our study, please fill out this survey: <Link for demographics survey and consent form>

We are thankful that you took the time to read through our request. If you do not wish to participate, simply ignore this email. We might send a follow-up, later, if we haven't heard from you, but the same note applies: we know you are very busy and may not wish to or may not have time to participate, and no reply needed if so.

Best regards,

[researcher]

Recruitment message for personal contacts

Hello [name],

I am part of <PI's> research team. As <PI> mentioned to you, we are studying how Security and Privacy (S&P) researchers consider and discuss the ethical implications of their research. We would like to invite you to a 60 minute interview to share your insights on ethical considerations in your research and within the S&P research community.

The interview will be conducted on zoom. We would like to record the interview and use de-identified transcripts for analysis. You can also opt to not be recorded, please let us know in advance if that is the case.

If you're interested, please fill out this survey and we can schedule an interview: < Link for demographics survey and consent form>

Thank you for taking the time!

Best regards

[researcher]

Recruitment text for cold emailing

Dear [name],

We are a research team from <University>. We are studying how Security and Privacy (S&P) researchers consider and discuss the ethical implications of their research. We would like to invite you to a 60 minute interview about your experiences with ethics in your research and in the broader Security and Privacy(S&P) research community.

The interview will be conducted on zoom. We would like to record the interview and transcribe it for further analysis in our study. Any personal information will be de-identified and only appear in the form of aggregated data in our research publication. You can also opt to not be recorded, please let us know in advance if that is the case.

If you're interested in our study, please fill out this survey: <Link for demographics survey and consent form>

Lastly, we are thankful that you took the time to read through this email. If you do not want to participate, please accept our deepest apologies and simply ignore this email.

Best regards,

[researcher]